

EFFECTIVE USE OF ACTION GAMES IN IMPROVING THE PHYSICAL FITNESS OF YOUNG VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract: The article contains information about the use of mobile games as a physical tool to improve the physical fitness of young volleyball players, as well as information about the series of national mobile games.

Key words: young volleyball players, physical training, action games, technical training.

INTRODUCTION

Mass participation in physical education and sports should become a daily need of schoolchildren, at the same time, the game of volleyball plays a role in the comprehensive development of schoolchildren, in forming a healthy lifestyle, and in raising them to become well-rounded people. , serves as the main factor in getting rid of lawlessness and other negative vices.

A lot of action games came from abroad and became nationalized. Because the content, purpose and essence of our religion corresponded to the climatic conditions of our country, the social work and living culture of the population. For this reason, it should not be surprising if there are opinions about the action games of other nations that are part of the national action games.

Based on the scientific-theoretical opinions of famous scientists M.Murodov, U.Koraboyev, MJabborov, J.Toshpolatov, A.Atoyev, R.Abdumalikov, T.Usmonkhoyayev and the contents of the games, national action games are divided into the following categories can:

1. Games related to natural scenery, science. Examples of such games as

"Plant Plant", "Potato Planting", "Rain", "Father Frost" can be shown. These games serve to educate the physical and mental qualities of the participants, such as vigilance, dexterity, endurance, based on actions such as the ability to avoid weather changes, cold and rain.

2. Games related to the animal world. This includes "Birds fly away", "The hawk has come, run away, my child", "Wolves and hunters", "Wolves in the zoo", "Geese", "Fox and rooster", "Itvaqaig'a". and many similar games are examples. In these games, together with virtues such as mutual relations, good and evil, and self-care, all physical qualities are cultivated. On this basis, children can be interested in the animal world and feel the need to protect it.

3. Games related to work. Human activity is determined by mental and physical work. They can also be found in the content of action games.

The series of mental work games includes "Counting games", "Write and think of numbers", "Say the name or item sequentially and in a shuffle", "Jump and sing", "Draw a picture quickly". , "Shape making" and similar activities include games.

There are also a lot of action games that reflect physical labor. Ulaiga "Cracking fire", "Herd ball" (shepherd), "Double plowing" (plowing the ground, running), "Hanging out", "Pulling", "Carrying", " The donkey rode", "Pedestrian race", "Train" and others. In their content, the ways of working, the methods of its implementation are embodied in qualities that express endurance.

In general, in all national sports games, mental and physical work are combined and mainly serve to educate physical fitness.

4. Complex and simple action games used in mass cultural events (holidays, weddings, various ceremonies, sports competitions, etc.), i.e. organized for the purpose of demonstration and competition. They include fighting elements, horse games, kopkari-ulak, racing, goalkeeping, stone lifting, tug-of-war, shoulder wrestling, "cockfighting" and others. enters.

5. Games that serve to train physical qualities are also divided into different categories. Examples include:

Games related to speed: "Trap", "Who is first", "Insiz kuyon", "Running on all fours" (crawling), "Stuttering birds", "The third is more", various relays and others;

Strength games: "White bone", "Chilik", "Shoulder kom-kai", "Donkey rode", "Tug of rope", "Wrist strength test", "Hand pull" and others;

Games about endurance: "White poplar, blue poplar", "Get out of the circle", "Alamon poyga", "Dorboz", "Lame crow", "Lover" (gardkam), "Swordsmen", "Five Stones", "Nine Stones", "Burn Your Back", "Bota Solde", "Tortishmachak", "Kozboglash", "Bekin-machak", "Who Came", "Zuv-zuv" » and others.

The complex and simple national games of the Uzbek people, whose names are mentioned above, along with training the physical qualities of people at all ages, directly serve to form and further improve human virtues in them.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In the development of qualities such as dexterity, compactness, perseverance, perseverance, and resilience in young volleyball players, one should not limit oneself to only active games in physical education classes. In their spare time, it is appropriate to ensure that they can freely engage in sports games, gymnastics, athletics, and wrestling in the yard, street, and fields. It is necessary to use the game in a timely manner.

The physical fitness of young volleyball players is the basis for the formation of skills, vital qualities and skills necessary for work and defense of the Motherland.

Combining the qualities of a YOUNG volleyball player, the individual abilities of athletes and their technical-tactical training in a purposeful manner ensures high sportsmanship.

Currently, physical training in all types of sports consists of two parts,

general and special. It serves as a basis for general physical training. In turn, technical training itself is a powerful tool for special physical training of all systems of the athlete's body.

When choosing general physical training equipment for young volleyball players, it is necessary to consider the following important rules.

Exercises should be close to the character of the nervous system of the volleyball player and the mode of operation of all the systems of the body. Exercises should help to develop special qualities. For example, some acrobatic exercises with elements of one-on-one combat, exercises performed in pairs with resistance from a partner, etc.

The exercise should be enriched with the development of movement coordination and various movement actions in changing situations. For example, sports games: volleyball, soccer, gymnastics, etc.

Exercises should serve for faster recovery of other movement and central nervous system activity of athletes. These include walks, cross-country, action games, leisurely sailing and other games that take place in the air under special conditions.

It is necessary to distinguish two groups of exercises in special means of physical training.

A) exercises aimed at developing specific muscle groups and qualities necessary for an athlete in volleyball.

B) exercises aimed at improving groups of volleyball techniques and technical elements of movements. In special physical training, it is especially important to develop the movement qualities necessary for a volleyball player and to improve the elements of volleyball technique. The following important rules should be taken into account when choosing and conducting exercises for a volleyball player's special physical fitness:

V) choosing exercises that correspond to the nature and structure of

movements and are directly related to static-dynamic exertion with movements. For example, individual movements of an athlete, imitation exercises, exercises in the form of a game, etc.

G) Using exercises aimed at developing certain muscle groups that perform the main thrust in their actions. Exercises with weights and on simulators for the development of leg and abdominal muscles.

Such a selection of special exercises develops a complex of movement qualities and improves the technical aspects of the athlete's movement.

The contingent of participants is their age, physical development, functional status before the start of training and the level of training;

The number of training sessions per week, per day:

Volume, intensity, level of mental effort and emotional activity of training work.

It is known from experience that most of the skilled volleyball players use enough general and special physical training during the training period, and during the competition they reduce them to a minimum or do not use general physical training.

Using comprehensive physical training tools throughout the year, including during the competition, combining it with technical-tactical and other types of training helps to increase sports skills and achieve high results.

It is especially important for volleyball coaches to correctly plan physical, technical and tactical training sessions during the year, periodic and individual training sessions, and coordinate their size and intensity.

Pedagogical requirements for the organization and conduct of mobile games in the use of mobile games as a physical tool for improving the physical fitness of young volleyball players.

Choose a game. A well-chosen game is an important condition for the success of education and training. When preparing for the game, the teacher must

determine the main tasks of the lesson, taking into account the composition of the participants, their age characteristics, as well as their physical fitness. Sometimes a good game is chosen, but it can go badly. Such situations occur as a result of not matching the interests and passions of the participants of the selected game, and the educational tasks are not fulfilled.

When choosing a game, the teacher should know how the training will be conducted (if it is conducted in the style of a lesson, the game will be conducted in its first, second or final part, during a break, etc.). If the game is held in winter, more active games should be chosen that will activate the students and evenly distribute the physical load.

The choice of the game is directly related to the venue. In small or not so large narrow halls, the game can be played while standing along the line, in which the participants of the game take turns. All games that can be played in a large hall or on a sports field will be played. If the game is played outdoors, it is necessary to take into account the weather and the temperature of the air (especially during winter). When the air temperature is low, all the participants of the game take an active part in playing the game, and the physical load is evenly distributed to all the participants. In the summer, in hot weather, it is better to use games with less movement or in which the participants take turns.

The choice of game also depends on the hardware required for the game. Not having this equipment for the game can prevent it from being organized.

CONCLUSION

It is an important task of the teacher to correctly determine the actions performed in the game. Before starting the game, it is necessary to take into account the nature of the work and the mood of the players. If the game is played after classes with physical or mental effort (supervision work or similar

activities), games with less or moderate movement should be chosen for young volleyball players.

During training, it is necessary to take into account the speed and general mobility of the games and alternate them. For example, it is useful to have a toss game after a game where all participants run at the same time.

Slowing down the pace of the game, that is, reducing the speed of movement in the game, is one of the ways to conduct the actions in the game at a certain standard. In the game, children are very excited to do physical exercises. Therefore, the teacher must not only act according to their mood, but also take into account the young characteristics, fitness and health of the volleyball players. The teacher should monitor the condition and actions of the players separately, and should not forget to control the game. The specific standard of actions is determined by the method of conducting the game, taking into account the conditions of the game.

Physical qualities of volleyball players are developed through the use of action games in improving the physical fitness of young volleyball players.

The efficiency of technical and tactical training of young volleyball players increases.

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